

BIOBLOCKS: CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL MADE FROM WOOD FIBREBOARD DUST

PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET

NIBIO
NORWEGIAN INSTITUTE OF
BIOECONOMY RESEARCH

smartpanel

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By transforming wood fibreboard dust into modular construction units, Bioblocks support circular buildings, extend material lifecycles, store carbon, and provide an alternative to conventional construction materials.

Bioblocks are modular construction units made from fibreboard dust, a by-product from sanding and routing fibreboards before their use in interior fittings. The dust is bound with a fully bio-based adhesive (citric acid and sorbitol).

APPLICATIONS

- Interior walls, including potential load-bearing structures.
- Lightweight design for adding one or two storeys to existing buildings.
- Modular system for fast and efficient construction.
- Integrated voids for reinforcement and utility installation.

ASSET

- Made from 100 % recycled fibreboard (MDF) residues with a fully bio-based binder.
- Comparable strength to conventional cement-based products, maintaining performance in wet and dry conditions.
- Lightweight design, enabling easy, mortar-free assembly.
- Integrated voids reduce weight and allow reinforcement or utilities.
- Lowers greenhouse gas emissions and stores CO² in building walls.

R&D CHALLENGES

- Expanding potential applications through testing of fire, thermal, acoustic, and VOC performance.
- Optimising product strength for structural applications.
- Scaling up production for cost-efficiency.
- Long-term wall monitoring to guide future improvements.

PARTNERS

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